

TEACHING GENDER STUDIES IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN 10: DEVELOPING, TESTING, AND PILOTING A MEASUREMENT TOOL FOR ASSESSING PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study developed and pilot-tested a tool that measures social studies teachers' PCK on gender studies in Naga City, Camarines Sur. The study used an exploratory sequential mixed methods design where it involved three distinct phases: initial qualitative phase, quantitative phase, and integration phase wherein the qualitative and quantitative results were consolidated to develop and recommend a tool for measuring PCK in gender studies. Four FGDs and three KIIs were conducted in the qualitative phase where content analysis was used to identify patterns and themes. A survey questionnaire was administered to 86 public and private social studies teachers in Naga City, Camarines Sur. Several testing methods were used in the quantitative phase such as reliability testing, Cronbach's α , validity testing, face validity, and content validity. Findings revealed that the essential constructs in assessing the PCK of teachers for *pedagogical knowledge* are *knowledge of learners, pedagogical contexts, educational environment*, while the *content knowledge* consists of *knowledge of subject matter* which is measured using *gender belief inventory*. The PCK tool results has an overall Cronbach's α of 0.931 which suggests that the tool consistently measures the intended constructs across various items. Meanwhile, the overall mean score resulted in 4.000 which shows that teachers have a high level of PCK in light of teaching gender studies. Recommendations from the participants suggest strategies to improve PK and CK on gender studies, as well as adopting the developed PCK tool. Improving teachers' PCK requires a curriculum review, proper training programs, and published resource materials.

Keywords: *Pedagogical Content Knowledge, PCK, Pedagogical Content Knowledge Measurement Tool, Gender Studies, Araling Panlipunan, Social Studies*

INTRODUCTION

Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) is a critical concept in education, defined as the teachers' understanding of effective ways to represent and explain subject matter to make it comprehensible to students (McComas, 2014). PCK helps identify the common concerns surrounding the teacher and teaching profession, particularly in transmitting the necessary knowledge about the subject matter to the students (Ofori et al., 2022). This means that for teachers to develop quality lessons and create a good classroom environment, teachers must adhere to a minimum standard regarding the subject-matter component and pedagogy (Shulman, 1986). Since PCK improves student outcomes and teaching, it is only necessary to develop a tool that measures it.

Similar to other academic fields, the effectiveness of the social studies curriculum is significantly influenced by the teachers' comprehension of the subject matter and the pedagogical approaches employed to convey it to students. Teachers who have limited pedagogical knowledge are reported to use inappropriate teaching methods and materials; while a limited content knowledge may introduce misconceptions about the topic (Najumba, 2013). This emphasizes the significance of providing social studies teachers with the necessary competencies to deliver the lessons effectively, particularly in terms of both pedagogy and content. Unfortunately, PCK-related research efforts have been concentrated more on mathematics and science and relatively few studies are conducted on social studies (Lotivio-Bedural et al., 2019).

In the context of teaching gender studies at Oglethorpe University in the United States, Tuininga (2016) noted not everyone had a strong understanding of its basic issues such as gender and development, gender roles, and other related facets. In this matter, developing a tool to measure PCK for gender studies will help assess the quality of the teaching. This is particularly necessary because as gender studies is relatively new in the DepEd curriculum, some teachers may not have been thoroughly trained yet they are assigned to teach this subject (Guerriero, 2017). Teaching gender studies also requires innovative approaches and an extended framework of knowledge within the ever-changing concepts and theories about this discipline (Geier, 2019).

Findings of previous studies highlight the importance of classroom observation tools to help assess quality teaching (Barrogo, 2020). However, scholars noted the following limitations of the DepEd classroom observation tool: (a) classroom observation tool is deemed too subjective (Castillo, 2021) and lacks sufficient emphasis on the subject matter's content (Barrogo, 2020). In light of PCK, the DepEd classroom observation tool seems to lack components that are recommended by educational theorists. Aside from subject matter content, other component lacking includes *knowledge of learners* where teachers need to understand the background of their learners before conducting classroom instruction. Using PCK as a guide, this study addressed the limitations of the existing classroom observation tool that aims to capture both pedagogical and content knowledge

To address these gaps, this study developed and pilot-tested a tool that measures social studies teachers' PCK on gender studies. Quality gender studies teaching is important because gender knowledge is a vehicle to uplift global awareness of pressing issues, including an establishment of a gender-responsive nation guided by gender principles and concepts.

PCK in gender studies, which is taught in the third quarter of grade 10 in junior high schools, anchored to the DepEd's Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in Araling Panlipunan 10 was the target content knowledge that was measured in the tool developed in this study. These are to: (1) discuss gender, sexuality, and gender roles in various parts of the world; (2) analyze discrimination against women, men, and LGBT (Lesbian, Gay, Bi-sexual, and Transgender); and (3) give importance to the response of the government and the citizens of the country on the issues of discrimination and violence.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop and pilot-test a PCK tool for teaching gender studies. To help achieve this objective, the study answered the following:

1. What are the essential constructs and variables for assessing the teachers' level of PCK in teaching gender studies?
2. How valid and reliable are the developed measurement tools for assessing the teachers' level of PCK in teaching gender studies?
3. What policy recommendation can be proposed to help PCK for gender studies be put in place?

METHODOLOGY

This study is done in Naga City, Camarines Sur and the participants are students, social studies teachers, and gender experts. Guide questions were used for the qualitative interview about their perception on PCK, specifically teaching gender studies. The participants were selected through purposive sampling. Four FGDs were conducted: five teachers from public school (FGD1), five teachers from private school (FGD2), five students from public school (FGD3), and five students from private school (FGD4). A total of 20 participants have undergone focus group discussion. The master teacher and three gender experts were interviewed individually. A total of 4 participants have undergone key informant interview. Based on the results of the FGD and interviews, a five-point Likert scale survey questionnaire was developed that captures teachers' attitudes and viewpoints towards their PCK in teaching gender studies, with 41 statements covering *knowledge of the subject matter, knowledge of learners, pedagogical contexts, educational environment, and gender belief inventory*.

The pilot testing was administered through Google Forms and was sent to all 91 public and private social studies teachers within Naga City, Camarines Sur. The study has a response rate of 95 percent (n=86) which was composed of 66 public school social studies teachers and 20 private school social studies teachers.

Content analysis was used for the qualitative phase to find patterns and themes from the interview of respondents in order to identify the essential constructs and variables of PCK in teaching gender studies. In the quantitative phase, several testing methods were used such as reliability testing, Cronbach's α , validity testing, face validity, and content validity to develop and pilot a PCK tool for gender studies teachers which is aligned to the objectives of the study. In the integration phase, the two datasets were analyzed to answer the research questions.

RESULTS

A. Essential Constructs and Variables for Assessing the Teachers' Level of PCK in Teaching Gender Studies According to Students, Teachers, and Gender Experts

<p>Construct 1: Knowledge of Learners</p>	<p>The findings of this study display that the variables of the construct, <i>knowledge of learners</i>, demonstrates that effective teaching necessitates an approach that accounts for the diverse needs, backgrounds, and learning styles of students. Continuous assessment of student progress is a pivotal element, ensuring that educators monitor each learner's trajectory and promptly address areas requiring additional support. Additionally, recognizing and embracing diversity among students is crucial. Teachers must harness a spectrum of pedagogical knowledge, respecting different learning styles, abilities, and backgrounds within the classroom. This commitment to diversity extends to the application of differentiated instruction, a key strategy enabling teachers to tailor their approach to meet the unique needs of each student.</p>
<p>Construct 2: Pedagogical Context</p>	<p>The variables under the construct, <i>pedagogical contexts</i>, emphasize the fulfillment of educational objectives by continual reference to the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). The efficacy of participatory methods such as recitation, reporting, and engaging activities that transform them from passive listeners to active contributors. Teachers should also acknowledge the challenges of addressing diverse perspectives and sensitive topics, emphasizing open dialogue to encourage respectful conversations. It was also revealed that the following pedagogical strategies can be employed, including reflective questions, constructivism theory, scaffolding theory, and differentiated instructions, tailored to the diverse needs of learners.</p>
<p>Construct 3: Educational Environment</p>	<p>The variables under the construct of <i>educational environment</i>, highlights that teachers should be guided by respectful discussion guidelines which are pivotal in handling classroom scenarios and ensuring acceptance and understanding of diverse perspectives. In addition, the importance of recognizing disengaging societal biases and conservatism among students would definitely help their understanding of the topics. Findings show that planning approaches</p>

	such as creating inclusive discussion, safe space for students, and incorporating games-based activities will enhance the learning environment.
Construct 4: Knowledge of Subject Matter	The variables under the construct, <i>knowledge of subject matter</i> , it is essential that teachers understand how their knowledge of subject matter can be transformed into a comprehensible knowledge that students would be able to easily understand. Moreover, educators are expected to be knowledgeable of the theories, perspectives, historical, and cultural contexts related to gender that would make up their subject matter knowledge. In addition, it is important to foster a respectful discussion especially towards individual gender identities.
Construct 5: Gender Belief Inventory	Under the construct, Gender Belief Inventory, the findings of this study supports DepEd's formulation of Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC), upon which these concepts were expressed by the respondents: <i>Basic concepts on gender, gender vs sex, stereotypes, gender roles, sexual orientations, gender identity, gender expression, and gender biases</i> . The competencies that teachers must impart to their students are measured through the integration of these concepts using the Gender Belief Inventory.

B. Validity and Reliability of the developed measurement tool for assessing the teachers' level of PCK in teaching gender studies

Table 1. Overall results on reliability and mean scores of the PCK tool developed

Results	Value	Interpretation
Overall Cronbach's α	0.931	Excellent
Overall mean	4.000	Above Average

Legend: PCK Scores: 1.00-2.33 Below Average, 2.34-3.67 Average, 3.68-5.00 Above Average

Table 2. Knowledge of learners

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
B1. I acknowledge my students' prior knowledge before starting class discussions.	4.512	0.699	0.805
B2. I make sure to understand my students' learning difficulties.	4.419	0.659	0.769
B3. I use assessment methods to evaluate my students' understanding of the topic.	4.267	0.658	0.749
B4. I use different approaches (questions, discussion, etc.) to find whether my students understand the topic.	4.337	0.644	0.761
B5. I provide supplementary activities to my students to facilitate understanding of the topic.	4.023	0.719	0.793

Table 2. Knowledge of learners

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
Overall	4.312		0.812 (Good)

Table 3. Pedagogical contexts

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
C1. I make sure my students clearly understand the objectives of the topic.	4.512	0.646	0.782
C2. I use different teaching methods to capture the interest of my students in the subject.	4.256	0.706	0.760
C3. I provide for my students to express their opinion freely in class.	4.547	0.680	0.787
C4. I use a variety of teaching approaches to transform subject matter into comprehensible knowledge.	4.198	0.610	0.763
C5. I use multimedia or technology (e.g. PowerPoint, videos) to express the concept of the subject.	4.523	0.715	(0.842)
Overall	4.407		0.823 (Good)

Table 4. Educational environment

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
D1. I provide an engaging learning atmosphere inside the classroom.	4.395	0.708	0.856
D2. I provide a conducive learning atmosphere inside the classroom.	4.314	0.673	0.851
D3. I pay attention to students' reaction during class and adjust my teaching attitude.	4.477	0.808	(0.903)
D4. I create classroom circumstance/motivational activities to promote my student's interest for learning.	4.221	0.640	0.864
D5. I cope with the classroom context appropriately.	4.163	0.611	0.864
Overall	4.314		0.891 (Good)

Table 5. Knowledge of subject matter

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
A1. I understand the necessary content to clearly teach gender studies.	4.058	0.925	0.913
A2. I understand the principles behind the gender concepts I teach.	3.953	0.825	0.893
A3. I understand how to select appropriate content for Grade 10 students.	3.884	0.913	0.902
A4. I can answer gender questions from my students.	3.860	0.948	0.903
A5. I can clearly explain the impact of gender topics and issues on society.	3.953	0.969	0.885
Overall	3.942		0.918 (Excellent)

Table 6. Gender belief inventory

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
Gender vs Sex E17. Understanding gender roles and gender inequality in society also requires considering race, ethnicity, and social class.	4.047	0.649	0.916
E4. Men need to be liberated from gender stereotypes as much as women do.	4.523	0.793	0.915
Stereotype and Gender bias E11. Women's lives would be improved if they lived professionally independent from men.	3.651	1.038	0.908
E15. There should not be different gender roles for men and women.	4.140	1.150	0.914
E2. Men and women's gender roles today are determined by the way that gender roles evolved for survival in			

Table 6. Gender belief inventory

	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
Gender Roles	hunting and gathering societies.	3.640	0.919	0.916
	E3. A man's first responsibility should be obtaining economic success, while his wife's first responsibility should be caring for the home and family.	3.802	0.865	0.917
	E5. Men's control over women forces women to be the primary caretakers of children.	3.372	1.030	0.909
	E6. Having women in positions of political power would bring about new systems of government that promote peace and cooperation.	3.965	0.694	0.915
	E8. Natural differences between men and women determine the different gender roles men and women occupy in society.	3.628	0.934	0.909
	E9. Class is more important than gender in explaining why women have not achieved equal leadership with men in society.	3.302	1.052	0.909
	E13. Gender is not natural; it is created as we do it.in the ways we dress, talk, behave, and use our bodies.	3.860	0.935	0.914
	E14. Boys should be taught to be rational, competitive, and self-assured to prepare			

Table 6. Gender belief inventory

	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
	them to enter the paid labor force and girls should be taught emotional qualities and sensitivity to others to prepare them for child rearing.	3.233	1.195	0.911
	E19. Men and women should be treated in a gender-neutral way, especially under the law.	4.128	0.665	(0.918)
Gender Expression	E12. Women's lives would be improved if they lived personally independent from men.	3.512	1.060	0.906
	E1. Gender inequality can be eliminated regardless of biological differences between men and women.	4.244	0.650	0.916
Gender Equality and Inequality	E7. Women's oppression can stop even if women and men live together.	3.093	1.224	0.908
	E10. Like women, men are also oppressed in our society.	3.674	1.011	(0.919)
	E16. Gender stereotypes are the only true source of women's oppression.	3.581	0.951	0.911
	E18. Women's hormones (i.e., estrogen, progesterone, and prolactin) are the key reasons why women are the appropriate primary nurturers and caretakers of children.	3.663	1.025	0.916

Table 6. Gender belief inventory

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
E20. Women are prevented from being leaders in government and business through men's control of political and economic institutions.	3.581	0.976	0.913
E21. Equality will come when we recognize the diverse range of possible sexes, so that one can no longer be seen as inferior and the other superior.	4.488	0.808	0.914
Overall	3.768		0.917 (Excellent)

C. Recommendations Emanating from the Study of Participants

This section is divided into two: the first section presents the recommendations provided by teachers in order to improve CK on gender studies and PK. The recommendations are classified into three: curriculum, training program, and resource material. The second one outlines the recommendation for adopting the developed tool to assess the teachers' PCK for gender studies.

DISCUSSION

A. Essential Constructs and Variables for Assessing the Teachers' Level of PCK in Teaching Gender Studies According to Students, Teachers, and Gender Experts

Construct 1: Knowledge of Learners

Knowledge of learners is important to be an effective teacher. In the study of Mitchell (2015), this construct considers the diverse needs, backgrounds, and learning styles of students, which the respondents also uphold. Another key aspect under this construct is conducting ongoing assessment of student progress to ensure that every learner is on the right track which one participant supports. Continuously assessing student progress is also recommended by Ozan and Kinkal (2018). They emphasize that by continuously evaluating the students' performance, teachers can identify areas of strength and areas that may need additional support, allowing for timely and targeted

interventions. Other than the continuous assessment of student progress, acknowledging the diversity among students is paramount, and teachers must harness various pedagogical knowledge to accommodate this diversity. This entails recognizing and respecting different learning styles, abilities, and backgrounds within the classroom. One way of recognizing the diversity of learners is by offering differentiated instruction (Rubach and Lazarides, 2021). In doing so, teachers are able to accommodate the unique needs of each student.

Construct 2: Pedagogical Contexts

Several effective strategies emerge from both teacher and learner perspectives. Teachers highlight the importance of regularly revisiting the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) to ensure all educational goals are met. Engaging students actively through participatory methods such as recitation, reporting, and activities fosters an inclusive learning environment, allowing them to feel involved rather than passive listeners. Practical experiences, such as dressing up according to preferred gender expressions, are cited as impactful activities, enhancing understanding by immersing students in the subject matter. Creating opportunities for learners to express their sentiments and opinions proves beneficial, especially for those struggling to keep pace with lessons. Pedagogically, as supported by the study of Zhubi (2022), varied approaches tailored to diverse learners, such as reflective questions, constructivism theory, differentiated instructions, and scaffolding, are employed in teaching gender studies to which the respondents of the study also mentioned.

Construct 3: Educational Environment

Establishing a conducive *educational environment* plays a pivotal role in the effective dissemination of gender-related topics within the classroom. This encompasses creating a safe space where students feel at ease posing questions and expressing their thoughts, fostering a supportive atmosphere free from judgment. Learners emphasize the importance of a positive classroom environment for effective learning, which is authoritative yet fosters a strong connection between teachers and students. Social Studies teachers, recognizing the societal biases among students, find it beneficial to momentarily disengage these biases to facilitate a deeper understanding of gender topics. Moreover, this is supported by Fu (n.d) acknowledging the diversity of learners, teachers address potential conservatism and sensitivity by employing knowledgeable approaches that create inclusive discussions accommodating varying beliefs. To enhance the learning environment, teachers incorporate diverse learning activities, encouraging critical thinking and constructive feedback.

Construct 4: Knowledge of Subject Matter

A teacher's proficiency in the *knowledge of the subject matter* in gender studies involves imparting foundational concepts to students. Beyond these fundamentals, emphasis should be placed on fostering an open, respectful, and accepting attitude toward individual gender identities. According to Vanner et al. (2022), teachers must also recognize the societal implications of gender in defining power, privilege, and opportunities, educators need to carefully introduce and explain these concepts, ensuring a nuanced understanding among students. This is supported by the study's findings,

which show that teacher's content knowledge extends to encompass deep insights into theories, interdisciplinary perspectives, and historical and cultural contexts related to gender. Understanding the basic principles and philosophies becomes paramount as they form the basis for comprehension.

Construct 5: Gender Belief Inventory

A teacher's mastery of gender content knowledge is paramount in navigating the intricacies of gender studies in the classroom. This expertise involves a profound comprehension of foundational gender concepts, including the distinctions between gender and sex, stereotypes, gender roles, sexual orientations, gender identity, and biases. A good teacher does more than just teach. They also stress the importance of giving up biases and encouraging an open and accepting view of different gender identities. Navigating sensitive topics like sexual orientation and gender expression requires both expertise and an inclusive teaching approach that encourages open dialogue and addresses students' curiosity with sensitivity.

B. Validity and Reliability of the developed measurement tool for assessing the teachers' level of PCK in teaching gender studies

Table 1: Overall results on reliability and mean scores of the PCK tool developed

The PCK tool results has an overall Cronbach's α of 0.931 which suggests that the tool consistently measures the intended constructs across various items. Meanwhile, the overall mean score resulted in 4.000 which shows that teachers have a high level of PCK in light of teaching gender studies.

Table 2: Knowledge of learners

Table 2 shows the construct *knowledge of learners* which has an overall mean score of 4.312=Above Average. The standard deviation of each item ranges from 0.644 to 0.719 which shows that responses are not spread out from the mean. Nevertheless, a high mean suggests that respondents acknowledge their student's prior knowledge, make sure to understand their students' learning difficulties, use varied assessment methods, employ diverse approaches to gauge student understanding, and provide supplementary activities to facilitate comprehension. The study conducted by Saubern et al. (2020) likewise found a high level of consensus among teachers regarding their self-perceived effectiveness in teacher's *knowledge of learners*, which suggests that their understanding of learner's background and needs are aligned to how they facilitate approaches inside the classroom. Cronbach's α is a measure of a group of items' internal consistency. A value closer to one indicates high internal consistency; while values close to zero indicate a low internal consistency. The overall Cronbach's α for *knowledge of learners* construct is 0.812 indicating "good" overall internal consistency between items.

Table 3: Pedagogical contexts

Table 3 shows the construct *pedagogical contexts* which has an overall mean score of 4.407 (Above Average). These scores suggest a positive self-assessment among teachers, indicating a favorable perception of their own instructional strategies and communication approaches. The standard deviation of each item ranges from 0.610

to 0.715 which shows that responses are not spread-out from the mean. The overall Cronbach's α for *pedagogical contexts* construct is 0.823 indicating "good" overall internal consistency between items. Examining individual items, C5 shows slightly higher value than 0.823, if item is deleted, meaning that the internal consistency of the construct *pedagogical context* will increase. However, interview with the students shows that the integration of technology in classroom is helpful in making them understand the lessons better since most of them are visual learners. The study of Basaran and Yalman (2020) supports this finding where the importance of technology-based methods is essential towards creating engaging and dynamic learning environments for students. Moreover, given the low increase in Cronbach's α , this item is recommended to be retained.

Table 4: Educational environment

Table 4 shows the construct *educational environment* evaluating the teachers' ability to create a supportive and engaging classroom atmosphere with an overall mean score of 4.314 (Above Average). The standard deviation also shows values ranging from 0.611 to 0.808 which is not so close to 1. This shows that responses are not spread-out from the mean. These scores suggest a consistently positive self-assessment among teachers, indicating a favorable perception of their own ability to create a positive learning environment in the context of gender studies instruction. The overall Cronbach's α for *educational environment* construct is 0.891 indicating "good" overall internal consistency between items. These findings are supported by the study of Zhai et al. (2020), where teachers' express confidence in providing an environment that captures students' interest, paying attention to their reactions and adjusting teaching attitudes accordingly, creating motivational activities, and appropriately handling the classroom context.

Table 5: Knowledge of subject matter

Table 5 shows the construct *knowledge of subject matter* which has an overall mean score of 3.942 (Above Average). The standard deviation of each item ranges from 0.825 to 0.969 which is closer to 1. This means data sets per item are spread-out from the mean. The mean scores suggest that while the performance is commendable, there is room for improvement, acknowledges the diversity of perspectives and experiences among the surveyed teachers, urging them to strive for an even better understanding and mastery of gender-related topics. The overall Cronbach's α for *knowledge of subject matter* is 0.918 indicating an "excellent" overall internal consistency between the items, suggesting that the questions reliably measure the underlying construct of subject matter knowledge. Same findings were found in the study of Karakaya and Avgin (2016) who explored teachers' self-confidence regarding their Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK), emphasizing the importance of content knowledge in effective teaching. Their research suggests that teachers with high self-confidence in their content knowledge are better equipped to deliver engaging lessons and address students' questions effectively.

Table 6: Gender belief inventory

Table 6 shows the construct *Gender Belief Inventory* which has an overall mean score of 3.768 (Above Average). The standard deviation of each item ranges from 0.649 to 1.224 which implies that items spread-out from the mean. These scores suggest a

range of attitudes among teachers, from less agreement on certain statements to strong agreement on others, indicating diversity in perspectives within the sample. Noteworthy is the variability in responses across different statements. For instance, the statement with the highest mean value (4.523) is E4 “*Men need to be liberated from gender stereotypes as much as women do*”, indicating a strong agreement among teachers on the need for liberation from gender stereotypes for both men and women. On the other hand, the statement with the lowest mean value (3.093) is E7 “*Women’s oppression can stop even if women and men live together*”, suggesting less consensus or agreement on this particular aspect. The overall Cronbach’s α for *Gender Belief Inventory* construct values is 0.917 indicating an “Excellent” level of internal consistency among the items. Few items are slightly higher than the overall Cronbach’s α like E10 (0.919) and E19 (0.918); however, these items were retained since the DepEd’s MELCs cover these topics about Gender Roles and Gender Equality. Supporting literature by Kim and Ko (2020) emphasizes the importance of content knowledge in shaping pedagogical practices. Their study on physical education teachers demonstrated that educators with a stronger content background tend to have more progressive and effective pedagogical approaches. This supports the idea that teachers’ beliefs and attitudes towards gender influence their teaching methods and classroom environments.

C. Recommendations Emanating from the Study of Participants

Recommendations provided by teachers in order to improve CK on gender studies and PK

Curriculum

The curriculum should encompass a broad range of topics, including but not limited to gender vs. sex, stereotypes, gender roles, gender expression, and sexual orientations. It should be designed to cater to various learning styles, ensuring that students receive a well-rounded education on gender that goes beyond basic definitions. Integrating diverse perspectives, historical contexts, and cultural impacts of gender throughout the curriculum can provide students with a nuanced view of the subject. In addition, a dynamic and responsive curriculum should evolve in tandem with societal changes and emerging research in gender studies. The study findings are supported by the study of Aviles (2022) where collaborative efforts involving educators, subject matter experts, and diverse stakeholders are essential to develop and refine a curriculum that aligns with contemporary understandings of gender and promotes inclusivity in educational settings.

Training Programs

Implementing effective training programs for teachers is essential to equip them with the necessary knowledge and skills to integrate gender studies into their pedagogy. These programs should cover a broad spectrum of topics, including foundational concepts in gender studies, teaching strategies for diverse classrooms, and addressing sensitive issues related to gender, sexuality, and identity. Workshops and professional development sessions can provide teachers with practical tools and resources, fostering a deeper understanding of gender-related issues and promoting inclusivity in their teaching practices. Ongoing training opportunities should be made available to ensure

that educators stay abreast of evolving gender-related discourse, societal changes, and advancements in the field of gender studies.

Resource Material

Developing learning resources in Filipino is crucial to support teachers in mastering the content without the added challenge of translation. Establishing guidelines for inclusive and diverse textbooks and learning materials that encompass a broad spectrum of gender perspectives is essential, especially since Grade 10 introduced gender studies topics to the curriculum, and as of 2017, no specific books have been published for public schools.

Proposed policy recommendations for adopting PCK for gender studies

Based on the validity and reliability of the constructs and indicators, this PCK tool can be recommended for wide-scale pilot testing to measure the level of pedagogical content knowledge of Social Studies Teachers in teaching gender studies. This will greatly help the Curriculum Implementation Division (CID) of DepEd Naga City, particularly for education program supervisor, and Social Studies teachers to measure, especially their gender content, where it can draw results and findings that can help improve classroom instruction and delivery through training programs.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it was revealed from the interviews that the essential constructs for assessing teachers' level of PCK are comprised of the following: *knowledge of learners, pedagogical context, educational environment, knowledge of subject matter, and gender content knowledge*. These are supported by the variables acquired from the interviews of various respondents such as teachers, students, and gender study experts. These findings are encouraging, suggesting that teachers generally feel well-equipped to create effective learning environments for gender studies instruction. These are supported by the students' perspectives as they find interest in the topic gender studies because of the pedagogical strategies applied by their respective teachers.

The developed PCK tool have undergone face and content validity testing from experts in the field of pedagogy and social studies. Revisions were made based on the feedback such as grammatical errors and content of the statement. All of the final statements incorporated in the tool were backed up by the interviews conducted by the researcher. The results of the pilot testing have undergone reliability testing, particularly Cronbach's α , where it resulted to "Excellent" suggesting that the tool consistently measures the intended constructs across various items. The measurement of teachers' gender content knowledge through the *Gender Belief Inventory* revealed a complex landscape of attitudes and beliefs related to gender roles, equality, and societal perceptions. These diverse responses underscore the importance of recognizing the complexity of teachers' attitudes and tailoring professional development initiatives to address specific nuances in beliefs related to gender.

The recommendations emanating from the study participants suggest strategies to improve PK and CK on gender studies, as well as adopting the developed PCK tool. Improving teachers' PK and CK requires a curriculum review in terms of planning and designing, as gender studies are new to the social studies curriculum. Thus, the curriculum for junior high school in *Araling Panlipunan*, as well as pre-service social studies teacher education programs should be thoroughly examined. This demonstrates that teachers should be provided with proper training programs to assist them assess gender-related topics and effectively teach them in the classroom. A published resource material for Grade 10 students in public school should also be released since there is no book or reference material provided for them. Advisory and support collaboration of gender study experts, teachers, and representatives from relevant organizations are highly encouraged to provide guidance on keeping the content up-to-date and culturally-sensitive to students. The developed PCK tool is recommended for wide-scale pilot testing to measure the PCK of social studies teachers, where the results can help improve classroom instruction.

Guided by the pedagogical content knowledge theory of Lee Shulman (1986), the results of these study shows that teachers effectively convey the subject matter, that is gender content knowledge, using the pedagogical knowledge they possess reflecting the high value of PCK scores. Since the RPMS CO rating tool lacks components from PCK supported by educational theories, Shulman's theory explains that there is a need to raise the standards for instruction and evaluation. Assessing *pedagogical knowledge* of social studies teachers comprises of *knowledge of learners, pedagogical context, and educational environment*. While, the *content knowledge* consists of *knowledge of subject matter* which targets their knowledge using the *gender belief inventory*. Hence, this highlights the necessity of the developed tool in teaching gender studies created by the researcher.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from this research, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the effectiveness of teaching gender studies in the Philippines.

Knowledge Generation

Future studies are recommended to conduct comparison of PCK in gender studies to selected demographic profiles such as their age, educational attainment, bachelor's degree, gender, years in service, and previous institution. This will help future studies assess the needs of the teachers on the specific demographics which will then serve as a basis on designing training programs appropriate for PCK of social studies teachers. School-based initiatives would greatly benefit their teachers depending on the target needs based on their findings.

This research also recommends future studies to test student outcomes to determine the effectiveness of the level of PCK of social studies teachers. A comparison

of the student outcomes using the RPMS CO rating tool and developed PCK tool will be beneficial. Future studies can also specify the gender score of the Gender Belief Inventory to know if social studies teachers will get the correct responses accurately. The Gender Belief Inventory can also be improved by including other genders aside from men and women.

Future studies can explore more on the overall Cronbach's alpha of the items covered in the PCK tool developed. From the findings, it resulted to 0.931 which indicates "excellent" where the items have high internal consistency. In addition, this research recommends to consider the use of Principal Component Analysis to validate the PCK tool developed. This validity test aims to ensure that the survey accurately measures the targeted variables by extracting the underlying factors from the questions to identify the principal components.

Encourage and support research initiatives focused on gender studies education in the Philippine context. This could involve providing grants for research projects, establishing research centers, and facilitating collaboration between researchers and educators. The aim is to contribute to the knowledge base, identify best practices, and generate evidence to inform future improvements in gender studies education.

Program Development

Social studies content is dynamic and subject to revision based on new research and societal changes. This study recommends that the Curriculum Implementation Division, particularly the Education Program Supervisor in Social Studies, to offer professional development opportunities for teachers to continue expanding their knowledge and skills in teaching gender studies. This could include workshops, seminars, conferences, and online courses focused on relevant topics in gender studies. This is to ensure that teachers have a solid understanding of key concepts in gender studies.

In addition, this study also recommends to provide teachers with a toolkit of pedagogical strategies specifically tailored to teaching gender studies. This could include techniques for facilitating discussions on sensitive topics, incorporating experiential learning activities, and using technology to enhance learning. The aim is to encourage teachers to employ a variety of teaching methods to accommodate different learning styles and preferences among students.

This study recommends the use of Ignatian Pedagogical Paradigm in teaching gender studies to facilitate discussions that challenge traditional norms and encourage students to think critically about gender issues. This can help create inclusive and safe classroom environments where all students feel comfortable expressing their perspectives, question assumptions, challenge stereotypes, and consider multiple perspectives.

Policy Formulation

This study recommends feedback mechanisms to continuously evaluate and improve the gender studies curriculum. This can involve soliciting feedback from students,

conducting regular program assessments, and incorporating insights from faculty and gender study experts. This will contribute to make the curriculum in gender studies updated.

Evaluation and feedback of the teaching methodologies utilized by social studies teachers must be evaluated by master teachers, department heads, or program supervisors. Feedback and reflections from them will contribute how a teacher will be adjusting their approach and strategies to create a supportive learning environment where diverse perspectives are valued and respected.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The respondents were given letters with approved permission by the school principals covered in the study. Informed consent forms (ICFs) were provided to both respondents in the interviews (focus group discussion and key informant interview) and survey where they were fully informed about the study's purpose, methodology, and their rights as respondents. Their signatures in the consent certificate served as a confirmation to their participation in the study.

The adult respondents were permitted to ask questions, and their willingness to engage. As stated in the ICFs, their answers were kept strictly confidential and were used to provide information and understanding about Social Studies teachers' PCK. The data obtained was saved in a password-protected data file that will only be seen by the researcher. Their involvement is voluntary, and they have the freedom to discontinue at any point without any consequences, bias, or loss of benefits. They can notify the researcher if they feel a certain amount of anxiety or if they have concerns when they participate in the research.

Parental consent was sought and required for student participants aged 15-17 to proceed with the interview. When parents agree to the provisions set by the researcher, they are asked to affix their signature on the consent form. The said provisions include parent or guardian's approval where they were fully informed of the purpose and risks of letting their child participate in the study. They were also given the opportunity to ask questions and their child's right to withdraw from participating was respected.

The information collected from the respondents will be stored for five years. The data will then be anonymized, meaning that all personally identifiable information and contextual information belonging to the participants will be removed. The data will be accessible to the researcher and thesis adviser during and until the completion of the project.

The researcher appropriately cited references and carefully presented the facts required. The research was assessed and granted approval by the Institutional Review Ethics Committee (IREC) of Ateneo de Naga University in order to guarantee adherence

to ethical standards. By considering these ethical considerations, the researcher can ensure that the study was conducted ethically and responsibly.

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